

PROSTHETIC REHABILITATION OF THE MAXILLARY DEFECT WITH INTERIM OBTURATOR- A CASE REPORT

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ABSTRACT

Restoration of the maxillofacial defects either intraoral or extraoral is very important as it affects the physical as well as the psychological status of the patient. Interim obturator is a transitional obturator mostly given after surgeries to aid in proper healing of the tissues and for adequate feed of the patient. This article describes a case report where interim obturator is given to patient operated for mucormycosis.

Keywords- Maxillofacial defects, Interim Obturator, Mucormycosis, Fungal infection

I INTRODUCTION

The pandemic of Covid 19 destructively affected the human health leading to various post disease complications. The spread of disease was very wide and left the long lasting impact on the individual. Mucormycosis turned up to be a very common fungal infection in patients who suffered from the Corona virus. Mucormycosis is caused by a group of microorganisms belonging to Glomeromycota phylum.¹ The symptoms of mucormycosis depend on where in the body the fungus is growing. The most common intraoral symptoms are sinusitis accompanied by nasal congestion, nasal discharge and sinus and bone necrosis.² Surgical intervention for the removal of the infection and prevention for spread of the disease is very important. In perspective of removal of the infection, various patient encountered the occurrence of oroantral fistulas and the palatal defects after surgery.

Maxillary defects are the irregular defects or malformations occurring in the maxillary bone and or soft tissues of the face. These defects can be either acquired or congenital deformities or may be due to any pathology. These defects results in problems like regurgitation of food, hypernasal speech, compromised esthetics and poor deglutition. Compromised health has a psychological impact on the patient. The affected oral and facial structures affects the behaviour of an individual in the society. Multidisciplinary approach plays a crucial role for good prognosis of the patient. If the maxillofacial defect is small it can very well be overcome by advanced surgical management. But for large defects surgeries followed by prosthetic reconstruction helps in favourable results.³

According to GPT 9 Maxillofacial Prosthesis is any prosthesis used to replace part or all of any stomatognathic and/or cranial structures.⁴

According to GPT 9- Obturator is a maxillofacial prosthesis used to close a congenital or acquired tissue opening primarily of the hard palate and / or contiguous alveolar /soft tissue structures. Prosthetic Rehabilitation of these intraoral maxillary defects is important as it creates a barrier between the nasal cavity and the oral cavity.⁴

Placement of surgical or interim obturators helps for good results of the definitive prosthesis as well as the confidence of the patient is maintained.⁵

Interim Obturators are placed after 7-10 days of surgery and helps in adequate healing of the constantly changing tissues and tender area. The primary purpose of Interim Obturator is unaltered deglutition and proper speech. Definitive prosthesis are given after 6 months of surgery depending on the complete healing of tissues.

II CASE REPORT

A 44 year old male patient was referred for the reconstructive prosthesis for a maxillary defect. Patient gave past medical history of surgical excision of the hard and soft tissues in the anterior hard palate for the mucormycotic infection. On intraoral examination Aramany class III defect was found with intact all the anterior and posterior teeth.(Fig.1) The patient was fed with ryles tube , hence he was unsatisfied with the meals. Hypernasal speech was evident due to oral and antral communication in the anterior palate. He could neither swallow food nor drink water. The patient was under psychological trauma. Extra orally the soft tissues on the anterior side were collapsed. Patient was informed about all the pros and cons of this prosthesis and consent was taken. After a thorough examination the surgical site was blocked with gauze dipped in betadine solution to avoid any unnecessary trauma to the healing tissues. The Preliminary impression was made with Irreversible Hydrocolloid Impression material Alginate (Prime Dental Products Pvt Limited) with the help of Perforated stock trays.(Fig.2) Type IV dental stone (Kalastone, Kalabhai Ltd. Mumbai, India) was used for pouring the impression. The designing of the Obturator was marked on the cast. The obturator was planned with multiple wrought wire clasps. The clasps were fabricated with the Orthodontic wire of 22 gauge round stainless steel and engaged in the retentive area of the teeth . Modeling wax was used to block the defective area and the palatal configuration was contoured.(Fig.3) The prosthesis was constructed on the same day to avoid any interruption which may be caused by tissue contraction or edema at the surgical site. Conventional fabrication was done using clear acrylic resin because clear acrylic helps us to distinguish the tissue impingement caused by the prosthesis.(Fig.4) The final prosthesis was inserted and checked for border extension.(Fig.5) Patient was asked to drink water and also eat food to check for the peripheral seal of the prosthesis, evaluate the leakage of water from the nose and the food accumulation from the nose respectively. Patient was also engaged in a routine normal conversation to check for hypernasality. The instructions for wearing and removal of the prosthesis was given .Hygiene maintenance instructions were also given to the patient. Night removal of the prosthesis was suggested.

III DISCUSSION

In maxillectomy patients, the use of obturator is crucial in recovering oral functions. The design of Obturator depends on the maxillary defect encountered in the patient. Obturator can be interim surgical or definitive. Obturators can be sectional, CAD/CAM made or hollow obturators. A hollow design of Obturators reduces the weight of the prosthesis facilitating in comfort to the patient. Obturators can be tissue supported ,tooth supported and Implant supported.^{6,7} The fundamental principles for Removable obturator prostheses include distributing stress over a wide area, employing a rigid major connector for cross-arch stabilization, and incorporating stabilizing and retaining components at strategic locations within the arch to minimize the risk of displacement due to functional forces.⁷ Dental Implants provides greater stability, functionality and esthetics to the obturators prosthesis.⁸ By multidisciplinary approach, regular follow ups and clinical expertise the patients can effectively overcome the challenges faced by the individual.

CONCLUSION

Maxillary defects are frequently encountered due to carcinomas, fungal infection and traumas and needs an immediate treatment. Multidisciplinary approach is of prime importance for the well being of the individual. Obturator either interim or definitive serves a boon in the palatal reconstruction avoiding the exchange of water n foodstuff between the nasal and oral cavity assisting the individual to live a healthy and confident life.

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Fig.1-Post surgical maxillary anterior defect

Fig.2- Impression of Maxillary and Mandibular arch

Fig.3- Blocked anterior defect and fabrication of the obturator

Fig. 4- Fabricated Interim Obturator

Fig.5-Intraoral Prosthetic view